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LG/LID: 720 Kyirong Tibetan

SOURCE(S): von Guttannen, Brigitte Huber. 2002. The Lende Subdialect of Kyirong Tibetan (Grammar & Glossary). Berne University Dissertation; available on the server

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Revised Word Questionnaire (Oct 2003)

Depending on the structure of the language, you may need to consult the questions in a reversed order (e.g. look at stress patterns before looking at phonological rules of assimilation, etc.)

For assistance with terms you can consult Bickel's Programm und Verzeichnis der verfügbaren Materialien (on the server)

Or, refer to the .pdf version of the Bickel & Nichols chapter on inflectional morphology (<http://www.uni-leipzig.de/%7ebickel/research/papers/index.html>)

PHONETIC & PHONOLOGICAL QUESTIONS

You should note forms that the author overtly *describes* (and also covertly *treats*) as phonologically independent. I am especially interested in the *crucial* differences between what is possible (or highly common) within a phonologically independent unit and what is possible at the *edges* or across boundaries

As you investigate, make an inventory-style comparison of patterns/processes that apply to independent forms with both lexical content and grammatical content. Note what is possible within the form's internal boundaries versus what is possible at the edges (especially is the form is polysyllabic). For example, note possible and required consonant onsets at the initial edge of an independent unit, and compare these to the same onset patterns within the unit. If an author says something like "no final consonants" or "no consonants in final position", always check to see if this constraint holds up at syllable edges *within* a phonologically independent form, and at the *ending* edge of the form itself.

Note also that a form may be phonologically "free" or independent, while not necessarily constituting a lexical category (i.e. "noun" or "verb" or "adjective"). I am especially interested in grammatical forms that are phonologically independent (and also lexical forms that are phonologically dependent upon something else—cannot occur alone phonologically, but they express a meaning that you might otherwise think of as "word")

Always take from the grammar at least 1 useful example of each thing.

Look for contradictory or conflicting phenomena (e.g. stress pattern A applies in almost all cases except...). This may be important. In some larger phonological units, one criterion may apply, but the other may suggest a different organization of units.

1. Segmental & Phonotactic Patterns (edges vs. internal)

--occurrence of segments, limitations, prohibitions

There is no mention of a phonemic glottal stop consonant, but glottal insertion happens before all vowel-initial words. Words cannot then be (phonetically) v-initial, but there are some v.v sequences word-medially (some of the few possibly monomorphemic disyllabic words in Kyirong) where no glottal stop-insertion is mentioned:

[p̣̌.ā:] 'mouse' [th̄.ā:] 'hammer'

vowels described as occupying 2 distinct syllables

and also one V-V combo with no glottal insertion mentioned either:

/ḳ̌:-o/ > [ḳ̌:o]

stop-FUT 'will stop'

apparently a word cannot begin with v:, even if intrusive nasal is present. from a look at the glossary, there are only fewer than 5 exceptions to this:

Q̣̌:-d̄ 'that one'

Q̣̌:-l̄ 'there'

*in these cases, the case/definiteness forms carry their own tones, so it may be that o: is a pword and the "suffixes" are phon free too. it seems that in certain di/polysyllabic word forms, word-initial *v:, but not always. For example, V-infl suffix can be CV:-CV. The prefixes are never mV:*

--voicing, aspiration patterns

voiceless aspirated phonemes do not occur word-medial onset (note that all forms greater than monosyllabic are probably bimorphemic, not sure if all bimorphemics are still analyzed as such by speakers however). So there is a voiceless aspirated devoicing process in word-medial onset position. This does also happen at compound boundaries. But does not happen at prefix-root boundary.

all word-initial voiced stops and affricates have intrusive nasal or prenasalization, along with slight devoicing of the stop/affricate. This also happens word-medially between adj roots -deriv suffix, between compounds and reduplicated forms. Also happens between prefix-root (never initial before prefix because only two prefixes are mV-).

/p/ > [p'] word-final (unreleased); also happens between compounds, but not at root-deriv. suffix boundaries and not applicable between root-infl suffixes because p changes in other ways.

--manner patterns (plosive, affricate, fricative, tap, approx, etc.)

--place (either specific like bilabial, lamino-dental, or general like anterior, coronal, etc.)

-- gemination

--vowel height/backness (quality)

--nasal vowels (see "rules") see other

-- vowel length see other

--VV sequences (includes diphthongs)

--idiosyncratic, segment-specific restrictions or possibilities, like "no labiodental approximants at starting edge, even though they occur medially etc."

2. "Rules" Part 1

Some phonological processes are restricted in application to the internal domain of a phonologically independent unit, and others are restricted to the boundaries/edges. Sometimes these differences are explicitly noted, others may be implicit. Please list the major processes that highlight such boundaries. Do these things happen to lexical forms only, to grammatical forms only, or to both?

Note types and locations of:

--vowel/consonant HARMONY/assimilation/dissimilation (note the types—place, manner, voicing, other)

unlike other Tibetan dialects, no vowel harmony at all in Kyirong, but there are some interesting vowel processes found between verb roots-infl suffixes. More like coalescence, not found in other morphological or syllabic combinations. There are 2 allomorphs of negative: mi- and ma-, but this is conditioned by aspect of verb, not by phonology.

There is one type of C place assim: a vowel with nasal or a VC_{NAS} will become Vŋ when before a suffix that is g-initial:

Also obs voice assim: a voiceless obstruent (after deaspiration) will become voiced if it follows another voiced segment. At first it seems like "voiced segments" don't include vowels, but some suffix onset voicing seems to happen (irregularly) following a root vowel. Not sure if this is the exact same voicing assim process though.

--segment DELETION/epenthesis, any kind of insertion/deletion processes

--segment METATHESIS or any type of re-ordering

3. "Rules" Part 2

Some rules referring to possible (and prohibited) syllable structures, processes of syllabification, and also to suprasegmental processes are sensitive to the domain of a phonologically independent unit. The distribution of these processes may help to define the boundaries and internal composition of such units.

Note:

--THE DEFAULT syllable template, and whether or not this template applies to the edges of phonologically free units. For example, a language may allow C clusters in coda position, but this may only happen at the ending edge of a phon. free unit, and not internally (or the other way around)

--C COMBOS—are the same types permitted both internally and at edges?

restricted CIC2 combos are permitted at word-initial edge, but not medially. Such combos are also prohibited for the initials of the 2nd element of a compound (which is interesting because in other ways compounds = 2 words, but here they behave just like any other inflected form). There are no suffixes (inflected or otherwise) with CC onsets; the prefix does not seem to have any effect on the ability of word-initial to have CC

these consonants can be coda both medially and finally: p, m, ŋ, j

k can be coda word-medial, but not word final. This includes SOME compounds, where k is not present, but in OTHERS, it is present. k is present at verb root-final only before 3 inflectional suffixes: -FUT, -VOL, -Q.Consent

--syllabification patterns (across syllables internally, vs. across morphemes, vs. across independent units)

--SUPER heavy syllables (Hall 2001). Can something that is phonologically free end with a super-heavy syllable? Or can such syllables only be in an internal position? What are the types (e.g. CV:C; CVVC: CVCC)? Can all types occur *anywhere* in a phon. free unit? Note even any seemingly idiosyncratic restrictions (like, might a certain suffix never co-occur with a SHS?, etc.)

--STRESS It might be a good idea to look at stress rules first, as these can often clearly illuminate boundaries of phonologically free units—especially if the language only allows "1 main stress per word" or something of that nature. You can then work "backwards" and look at other cues to independent status.

--is there a primary stress rule? what is the domain?

--what types of forms are included, what is exempted?

--what are the minimal/maximal domains for stress to apply? Can a phonologically free unit that is simply (C)V take the main stress?

--can only lexical forms take a main stress, or can independent grammatical forms also take it?

--TONE Again, another good starting place if other cues are hard to find. Is the domain of tone a syllable? morpheme? phonologically free unit? If the language has syllabic tone, there may still be a word-level domain at work, like "only 1 high per phon. free unit" or something else like this. If grammatical forms take tone, do they also have other features that might suggest that they can stand alone phonologically (like the other stuff listed above)?

A typical Tibetan-type phonation & pitch tone system. Mid tone corresponds with +voiced obs and breathy phonation (and mid-low pitch); High tone corresponds with -voiced aspiration and modal phonation (and high pitch). High, mid and low tones can have voiceless unasp obs initials. There are register/level tones (high mid low) and contour tones (hi fall mid fall low fall, with downward symbol `). A syllable cannot have low tone, breathy phonation and begin with a continuant, and there are no vowel-only syllables that are low/breathy. Not many words are voiced initial with a high tone, but it does happen sometimes.

Contour tones occur in monosyllabic words and on word-final syllables. Contour tone often found with nasalized vowel and always on a long vowel.

All open-class words have tone, and some grammatical markers also carry tone

In disyllabic forms (probably old lexicalized compounds, but not other forms it seems)

there is tone neutralization on the 2nd syllable to a default high pitch

Thus:

po: + dawa (Tibet + month) > [po:nda] 'Tibetan month'

But there are some exceptions:

prefix-root do not show this mi-d_o > [mi-nd_o] (NEG-go)

some compounds show falling tone on s2:

cī: + dz_ugū [cī:ndzù] (middle + finger) 'middle finger'

most inflectional suffixes aren't marked for tone "a-tonal"--don't carry default pitches, and don't seem to affect pitch of tone-bearing units that are adjacent

1 derived noun: p_omò: (alternates with p_omō:) 'girl' (presumably Tibet-FEMDERIV)

one inflectional suffix that seems to always carry a falling tone:

thù:-sã: 'met-AOR.Q' (note here also an exception to the contour tone neutralization, described below)

at least 1 case of free variation:

t_u^hŋ-gōnu: beat-IPFV.SENS

vs.

tsà:-gonu: beat-IPFV.SENS

in one case there is a default 'hi' on the disyll suffix; in other case there is no tone on disyll suffix.

This happens often enough that it may not just be transcription error.

Huber describes a tone neutralization pattern with contour tones: in disyllabic forms, contour tones never on initial. For example with compounds, if the first element carries a contour tone when alone, this is neutralized in the compound.

Thus:

mà: + mī [mā:mī] (fighting + person) 'soldier'

Also applies to derived noun forms:

pø: - pā [pø.pā] (Tibet - NOM) 'Tibetan person'

note also the default high tone on the 2nd syllable.

But there are exceptions to this process too:

mĕ:-de 'said-NF' 'saying' (not sure if transcription here is phonemic rep or phonetic)

zj̄-so 'looked-AOR.SENS'

t^hu:-sã: 'met-AOR.Q'

if these are phonetic transcriptions, then they represent exceptions to the initial syllable contour neutralization process. And note also that the last example represents an exception to the 2nd syllable default high pitch process.

--"PITCH ACCENT" In some languages, the apparent tonal contrasts are not clearly defined until they occur on a "larger" unit. Describe the morphological and/or syllabic complexities of such units

4. Minimality & Maximality

Look at the grammar, look also at the dictionary/glossary entries if they are included. What is the most common (or only) minimal and maximal size of a phon. free unit? Or alternatively, what is the minimal/maximal morphological complexity/composition of something that is phonologically free? (C)V? CV (with an initial crucially present)? di- or polysyllable? How big can a free unit be in terms of syllable number? Do these size constraints apply only to lexical forms? If there are constraints, must a lexical form be bimorphemic to be free? If so, what morphemes qualify? Any & all?

minimal word can be CV

sā 'place'

Huber analyzes evidential forms as mono-polysyllabic independent word-types.

Evidentials: don't participate in phon processes across their word boundaries, but internally and as a unit they show voice assim, place assim, no contour tone on initial syllable, default high pitch on 2nd, all other rules n/a

T/A markers: often homophonous with evidential markers. Can be mono-polysyllabic. They do participate in voicing assim with the verb stem (but sometimes in idiosyncratic ways), and they have their own internal voicing assimilation. There is also final k-emergence between the verb stem and a couple of inflectional affixes (always monosyllabic); 1 monosyllabic infl suffix assigned its own tone, but also participates in voicing assimilation with verb

5. Reduplication

Is the entire unit copied? More? Less? Can something of any phonological size/complexity have reduplication (even if the process is semantically restricted)? If there are different types of

reduplication, see if you can find patterns, or note what the author says.

Is the resulting suprasegmental pattern of a reduplicated form the same or different from a single free form? (Are there 2 main stresses or 1? 2 tones? a different tone altogether?)

reduplications have the very same phonological properties as compounds

6. Other Questions

Note any discussion & descriptions of phonological boundaries attributed to interruption or pause phenomena. Also note if the author argues for boundaries because of repair phenomena. Examples. Only in the more detailed grammars will you probably see such discussions.

7. Phonological Units in Morphologically Complex Forms

--COMPOUNDING: note any patterns of segmental alteration with compounds—especially at the edges of compounds; note prior and resulting stress/tone patterns; note segmental restrictions in compounds (e.g. in Manange, the 2nd element may never have an aspirated onset, even if the onset of the form when it is free is aspirated).

Again, note any conflicts of properties (e.g. in Lhasa Tibetan, a compound has 2 tone contours, but there is vowel harmony that spreads across the entire compound, and only a single main stress)

Sometimes in a compound, a piece of one of the elements may be deleted. If this happens, note any patterns, because this may suggest that one of the elements is in fact not a single phonological unit.

--"SIMPLE juxtaposition or concatenation of 2+ independent forms"—these are things that might be called "serialization" in some grammars: note any phonological discussion of these things. single tone? single stress? segment changes? ordering restrictions? co-occurrence restrictions?

--MULTI-morphemic forms: this is already discussed in above sections, but note especially phonologically free units that are minimally bimorphemic (or bigger), note any allomorphy that suggests that multi-morphemic forms behave as a single phonological unit.

--IF a language has a wide variety of inflectional affixes, do all stem-affix combinations have the same/similar stress, syllabification, segmental patterns, phon rules, tones, etc? Describe those that deviate from the set "general" patterns. Give examples. In German, for example, a stem + certain suffixes behaves as a **single** phonological unit ([li:.bɪx] 'love 1.sg'), but a stem + certain other suffixes behaves as **2** phonological units ([li:p.liç] 'dearly')—the resyllabification & voicing of the plosive is evidence of this.

Be sensitive to exceptions/variations in segmental/phonotactic, prosodic rules that may suggest that certain things "go together" phonologically, and others that do not. Explicitly state the conditions under which variations apply.